

SEARCH FOR NEW LOCAL ANAESTHETICS. PART II

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Several piperidino-, diethylamino- and morpholino-acetyl and -propionyl derivatives of alkyl *p*-aminobenzoates have been synthesised to study their local anaesthetic activity.

A series of alkyl *p*-aminobenzoates, when tested against goldfish, showed local anaesthetic activity, and both the activity and toxicity of the compounds increased with the increasing molecular weight of alkyl group (Adams *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, **48**, 1758). Esterification of *p*-aminobenzoic acid by various tertiary amine-alkanols led to the synthesis of procaine and its analogues, showing high local anaesthetic activity (Einhorn and Uhlfelder, *Annalen*, 1909, **371**, 131; Vliet and Adams, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, **48**, 2158; Adams *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1937, **59**, 2248). Since basic anilides having lypholytic and hydrophillic moieties also showed local anaesthetic activity (Lofgren, *Chem. Abs.*, 1937, **31**, 7854; Gaird *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1910, **17**, 400, 600), it was thought of interest to convert the amino group in alkyl *p*-aminobenzoates into a basic anilido group, yielding compounds of the general formula (1).

These compounds have an ester and a basic anilido group, and the acylation of amino group is expected to decrease the toxicity. The presence of propyl, isopropyl and *n*-butyl group in the ester part well balances the activity and the toxicity in the molecule.

For the preparation of compounds of type (1), alkyl *p*-aminobenzoate was treated with chloroacetyl chloride or β -chloropropionyl chloride. The resulting chloroacylated compound was then condensed with a secondary amine in absolute alcohol. The bases were finally converted into their hydrochlorides. Some of the hydrochlorides being uncrystallisable sticky masses, the bases were converted into the hydrobromides.

EXPERIMENTAL

isoPropyl p-(Chloroacetamido)-benzoate.—Chloroacetyl chloride (11.3 g.) in dry benzene (30 c.c.) was gradually added to *iso*propyl *p*-aminobenzoate (17.9 g.) in dry benzene (50 c.c.). The reaction mixture was heated under reflux for 4 hours. Benzene was removed by distillation and the residue washed first with dilute HCl and then with sodium bicarbonate solution, followed twice with water. The product was crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 60°-80°) in small needles, m.p. 100° (Found: N, 5.19; Cl, 13.95. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2\text{NCl}$ requires N, 5.47; Cl, 13.9 per cent).

TABLE I

Compounds.	Crystallised. from.	M.P.	Mol. formula.	Found.	Analysis. Calc.
<i>iso</i> Propyl- <i>p</i> -(diethylamino-acetamido)-benzoate-HCl	Absolute alcohol	206°	C ₁₆ H ₂₅ O ₃ N ₂ HCl	N: 8.75% N: 8.17	8.56% 8.17
<i>iso</i> Propyl- <i>p</i> -(N-morpholino-acetamido)-benzoate-HCl	Acetone	220°	C ₁₈ H ₂₉ O ₃ N ₂ HCl	Cl: 9.7	10.3
<i>iso</i> Propyl- <i>p</i> -(β-chloropropionamido)-benzoate	Alcohol	125°	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ O ₃ NCl	C: 58.27% H: 6.15	57.89 5.93
<i>iso</i> Propyl- <i>p</i> -(β-N-piperidino-propionamido)-benzoate	Pet. ether (40°-60°)	78°	C ₁₈ H ₂₆ O ₃ N ₂	N: 5.10 N: 8.11	3.19 8.6
<i>iso</i> Propyl- <i>p</i> -(β-diethylamino-propionamido)-benzoate-HBr	Acetone	188°	C ₁₇ H ₂₇ O ₃ N ₂ HBr	N: 7.42% N: 5.2	7.21 5.2
<i>iso</i> Butyl- <i>p</i> -(chloroacetamido)-benzoate	Pet. ether (80°-100°)	115°	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₃ NCl	Cl: 13.32 N: 8.78	13.17 8.8
<i>iso</i> Butyl- <i>p</i> -(N-piperidino-acetamido)-benzoate	Pet. ether (40°-60°)	86°	C ₁₈ H ₂₆ O ₃ N ₂	N: 7.97	8.42
Hydrochloride of the above base	Acetone-ether	228°	...	...	...
<i>iso</i> Butyl- <i>p</i> -(diethylamino-acetamido)-benzoate-HCl	Absolute alcohol	153°	C ₁₇ H ₂₆ O ₃ N ₂ HCl	N: 8.1 Cl: 10.3	8.17 10.36
<i>iso</i> Butyl- <i>p</i> -(N-morpholino-acetamido)-benzoate	Dil. alcohol	90°	C ₁₇ H ₂₄ O ₃ N ₂	N: 8.7	8.75
<i>iso</i> Butyl- <i>p</i> -(β-chloropropionamido)-benzoate	Pet. ether (60°-80°)	112°	C ₁₄ H ₁₈ O ₃ NCl	N: 5.38	4.96
<i>iso</i> Butyl- <i>p</i> -(β-N-piperidino-propionamido)-benzoate	Alcohol	77°	C ₁₉ H ₂₄ O ₃ N ₂	N: 7.97	8.42
Hydrochloride of the above base	Acetone-ether	210°	...	...	...
<i>iso</i> Butyl- <i>p</i> -(β-diethylamino-propionamido)-benzoate	Dil. acetone	87°	C ₁₈ H ₂₈ O ₃ N ₂	N: 8.25	8.75
Hydrobromide of the above base	Acetone-ether	201°	...	...	...
<i>iso</i> Butyl- <i>p</i> -(β-N-morpholino-propionamido)-benzoate	Pet. ether (60°-100°)	110°	C ₁₈ H ₂₄ O ₃ N ₂	N: 8.25	8.36
Hydrochloride of the above base	Acetone-ether	218°	...	...	...
<i>n</i> -Butyl- <i>p</i> -(chloro-acetamido)-benzoate	Pet. ether (40°-60°)	80°	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ O ₃ NCl	N: 5.36 Cl: 12.95	5.2 13.17
<i>n</i> -Butyl- <i>p</i> -(N-piperidino-acetamido)-benzoate	Alcohol	88°	C ₁₈ H ₂₆ O ₃ N ₂	N: 8.4	8.75
Hydrochloride of the above base	Acetone-ether	192°	...	...	...
<i>n</i> -Butyl- <i>p</i> -(diethylamino-acetamido)-benzoate-HBr	Do	135°	C ₁₇ H ₂₆ O ₃ N ₂ HBr	N: 7.25 Br: 20.0	7.23 20.5
<i>n</i> -Butyl- <i>p</i> -(N-morpholino-acetamido)-benzoate	Pet. ether (40°-60°)	66°	C ₁₇ H ₂₄ O ₃ N ₂	N: 8.65	8.75
Hydrochloride of the above base	Acetone-ether	100°	...	...	...
<i>n</i> -Butyl- <i>p</i> -(β-chloropropionamido)-benzoate	Dil. alcohol	93°	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ O ₃ NCl	C: 56.78 H: 6.26	56.25 6.34
<i>n</i> -Butyl- <i>p</i> -(β-N-piperidino-propionamido)-benzoate	Pet. ether (40°-60°)	62°	C ₁₉ H ₂₆ O ₃ N ₂	N: 4.93 N: 8.35	4.93 8.42
Hydrochloride of the above base	Acetone-ether	208°	...	...	...

isoPropyl p-(N-piperidino-acetamido)-benzoate.—A mixture of piperidine (1.7 g.), *isopropyl p-(chloroacetamido)-benzoate* (2.55 g.) in 2:1 molecular proportion in absolute alcohol (40 c.c.) was refluxed on a water-bath for 5 hours. Alcohol was recovered by distillation and the residue dissolved in dilute HCl. It was filtered and the filtrate made alkaline with ammonium hydroxide solution. The base was collected, washed with water and crystallised from dilute alcohol. It was recrystallised from petroleum ether (40°-60°) in long needles, m.p. 80°, yield 2.6 g. (Found: N, 8.75. $C_{17}H_{24}O_2N_2$ requires N, 9.21 per cent).

Hydrochloride of the above Base.—The base (2 g.) was dissolved in absolute alcohol (20 c.c.) and the solution saturated with dry HCl. Alcohol was removed by distillation and the residue crystallised from acetone-ether mixture, m.p. 235-36°. The other analogues synthesised in a similar manner are shown in Table I.

Hydrochloride of *isobutyl p-(N-piperidino-acetamido)-benzoate* was tested for local anaesthetic activity at the Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow. It showed no surface anaesthesia when applied to the cornea of guineapigs in 3% solution. However, for intradermal anaesthesia in 2% solution in normal saline, the action lasted for 60 minutes. It produced inflammatory reaction also. The compounds are being further studied for their pharmacological activity.

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Received July 24, 1955.